

Verification of Haldane Conjecture for Lower Spins via Density Matrix Renormalization Group

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The Haldane conjecture states that Heisenberg spin chain with half-integer spins are gapless, while those with integer spins are gapped. Using Density Matrix Renormalization Group, we verified the Haldane conjecture for lower spins by calculating the energy level differences, analyzing the scaling behavior of the entanglement entropy with system size, and examining the decay of the spin-spin correlation function.

I. INTRODUCTION

Condensed matter physics investigates systems with a large number of interacting particles, where the size of the Hilbert space grows exponentially with the number of particles. For example, even in a simple spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ chain, the Hilbert space size is 2^L , which quickly exceeds current computational capabilities when interactions between particles are explicitly accounted for. Understanding the many-body interactions in such systems is essential for studying important physical phenomena in strongly correlated systems, such as Mott transitions [1], high-temperature superconductivity [2], and the fractional quantum Hall effect [3]. This computational limitation has motivated the development of various approximate methods, each with its own challenges. For instance, the perturbation theory is only valid in the absence of strong interactions, while Quantum Monte Carlo methods suffer from the sign problem, restricting their use in fermionic and frustrated quantum spin systems [4].

Spin chains with Heisenberg interactions serve as a simple example of such strongly correlated systems. In this study, we focus on a key statement regarding Heisenberg spin chains: the Haldane conjecture. Proposed by Duncan Haldane in 1983, the conjecture states that Heisenberg spin chains with integer spins are gapped, while those with half-integer spins are gapless [5, 6]. The Haldane conjecture has provided significant insights into understanding topological phases in one dimension and has inspired extensive research. For example, study have shown that the Haldane phase is one of the simplest known topological phase. Later it was discovered that the odd-spin Haldane phase is topologically non-trivial, protected by at least three global symmetries, while the even-spin Haldane phase is topologically trivial [7].

The Density Matrix Renormalization Group (DMRG) is a numerical method that optimizes a quantum state defined on a lattice by iteratively updating a small local set of sites. After each local optimization, weak entanglement between are removed by discarding the sufficiently small singular values. DMRG has proven highly effective across a wide range of physical problems, establishing itself as one of the most reliable computational methods in condensed matter physics. Its applications span quantum spin systems, such as the Heisenberg model, the Ising model [8], and the Kivaev

honeycomb model [9], and interacting fermion systems such as the Hubbard model [10, 11]. DMRG has also been successfully applied to lattice field theory models, such as quark-meson interactions in the Schwinger model [12].

Although DMRG was initially developed independently of tensor networks, Östlund and Rommer showed in 1995 that the wavefunction produced by DMRG can be represented as a Matrix Product State (MPS), a specific type of tensor network state [13]. In the diagrammatic representation of tensor network, the MPS is characterized by that the tensors are connected sequentially, forming a 1D chain [14]. In this paper, we will discuss DMRG only within the framework of MPS, but it is important to note that DMRG can also be regarded as an independent computational method.

In this paper, we first introduce the relevant theoretical background on tensor networks and the DMRG algorithm, focusing only on the conclusions that are directly related to our study. Derivations are provided in the appendix. We then describe our approach to verifying the Haldane conjecture through three aspects: the energy difference between various energy levels, the scaling behavior of entanglement entropy, and the decay of the correlation function. Finally, we present our DMRG calculations for each aspect and compare our results with the theoretical predictions for gapless and gapped systems. The calculations in this study are implemented with the ITensor library [15].

II. THEORY

A. Tensor Network

A tensor network is set of tensors together with an instruction of how to contract them. Several important algorithms, including DMRG, can be implemented using tensor network formalism. An intuitive and insightful way of understanding tensor networks is through the diagrammatic representation. In the diagrammatic representation, a tensor is represented by a geometric shape, such as a circle or a square. Each leg connecting to the geometric shape represents an index of the tensor. For example, a matrix, which is a rank-2 tensor, has two legs. When a pair of legs from two tensors are connected, it means the corresponding indices are contracted. For instance, the product of two

matrices can be represented by connecting one pair of legs from two different rank-2 tensors. (see Fig. 1).

In principle, a tensor network can have any geometry, with each configuration defining a specific set of tensors and contraction rules. However, in practice, certain geometries are better suited as ansatz for specific physical models. For example, Matrix Product States (MPS) are particularly well-suited to simulate one-dimensional gapped systems. Projected Entangled Pair States (PEPS) are effective in capturing the entanglement structure of low-energy eigenstates of 2D local gapped Hamiltonians. The Multiscale Entanglement Renormalization Ansatz (MERA), which introduces an additional holographic dimension encoding a renormalization scale, is closely related to entanglement renormalization and is believed to have connections to the AdS/CFT correspondence in quantum gravity [16] (see Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Examples of simple tensors represented in tensor network graph notation. A vector (left), a matrix (middle), the product of two matrices (right)

Figure 2. Different type of tensor networks: (a) Matrix Product State (MPS). (b) Projected Entangled Pair State (PEPS). (c) Multiscale Entanglement Renormalization Ansatz (MERA).

B. MPS and MPO

Consider a generic quantum state, whose basis vectors are characterized by n indices:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n} c_{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n} |\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n\rangle \quad (1)$$

For example, in a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ chain of size n , each σ_i corresponds to either $|\uparrow\rangle$ or $|\downarrow\rangle$. This state can always be decomposed as a Matrix Product State (MPS) using successive Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) (see

Appendix A):

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n} \sum_{a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}} A_{a_1}^{\sigma_1} A_{a_1, a_2}^{\sigma_2} \dots A_{a_{n-2}, a_{n-1}}^{\sigma_{n-1}} A_{a_{n-1}}^{\sigma_n} |\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n\rangle \quad (2)$$

Similarly, any Hamiltonian written in this basis can be decomposed into a Matrix Product Operator (MPO). An MPO is a chain of connected tensors of the same length as the corresponding MPS, but with an additional physical index σ'_i at each site i . When this MPO acts on an MPS, it produces another MPS (see Fig. 3).

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H} &= \sum_{\vec{\sigma}, \vec{\sigma}'} c_{\vec{\sigma}, \vec{\sigma}'} |\vec{\sigma}\rangle \langle \vec{\sigma}'| \\ &= \sum_{\vec{\sigma}, \vec{\sigma}'} \sum_{a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}} W_{a_1}^{\sigma_1, \sigma'_1} W_{a_1, a_2}^{\sigma_2, \sigma'_2} \dots W_{a_{n-1}}^{\sigma_n, \sigma'_n} |\vec{\sigma}\rangle \langle \vec{\sigma}'| \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where we have adopted the more compact notation $\vec{\sigma} = \sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n$. For a detailed derivation and a different but more practical method for writing down Hamiltonian MPOs for spin chain systems, see Appendix B.

Figure 3. Diagrammatic representation of an MPO (squares) acting on an MPS (circles). By contracting all the primed indices, we obtain a new MPS with physical indices σ_1 through σ_n .

MPS is highly effective in simulating 1D system because it is a good ansatz for 1D states satisfying the area law. The area law states that when a system is bipartitioned, the entanglement entropy between the two parts scales as the area of their interface. The area law is shown to hold for low energy eigenstates of local gapped Hamiltonian in 1D, and are believed to be also true in 2D [17]. For example, according to Haldane conjecture, integer spin chains are gapped so has to follow the area law, while half integer spin chains are gapless thus not constrained by the area law. In section III B, we will see that our result agrees with the area law.

C. DMRG Ground State Search

Finding the ground state is essentially a problem of minimizing the energy $E = \frac{\langle \psi | \hat{H} | \psi \rangle}{\langle \psi | \psi \rangle}$. DMRG addresses this by performing the minimization locally on a small number of sites, typically two at a time, then sweep back and forth through the MPS to obtain the global MPS with the lowest possible energy. After each optimization, singular value decomposition will be performed on the local sites we are

optimizing. The singular values thus obtained represent the entanglements between the two parts of the MPS split at the current sites. Hence, weak entanglement states can be removed by discarding small singular values, keeping a small set of parameters that best describes the behavior of the entire MPS. Details of the sweeping procedure and the derivation of the equations used in optimization are provided in Appendix C 1 [18].

III. METHODS AND RESULTS

In this study, we verify the Haldane conjecture for lower spins in three ways. Firstly, we calculate the energy difference between levels for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin-1, expecting that the energy difference vanishes for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ but not for spin-1. Secondly, we examine the scaling of entanglement entropy with system size N for spins up to $\frac{3}{2}$, we expect that the entanglement for spin-1 saturates at a certain L , while those for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ do not. Finally, we calculate the decay of the correlation function for spins up to 2, we expect polynomial decay for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ but exponential decay for spin-1 and spin-2. Details of our calculations and results are provided in the following subsections.

A. Energy Gap

The Haldane conjecture states that Heisenberg chains with half-integer spins are gapless, while those with integer spins are gapped. By gapless we mean that the energy difference between energy levels approaches zero as the system size tends to infinity (the thermodynamic limit). Conversely, "gapped" implies the existence of a finite energy difference between certain energy levels, even in the thermodynamic limit [20].

In this study, we aim to calculate the first four energy levels of a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ chain and demonstrate that their energy differences vanish at thermodynamic limit. Additionally, we calculate the first five energy levels of a spin-1 chain and find two energy levels with a non-zero gap. The simulated energy difference between two energy levels depends on both the system size and the bond dimension, insufficient system size or bond dimension can cause our simulated result to deviate from theoretical prediction, so it is crucial to ensure that our results accurately reflect the behavior of the system in the limit of infinite system size and bond dimension.

To extrapolate to the thermodynamic limit, we plot the energy difference as a function of the inverse system size $\frac{1}{N}$. The intercept with y-axis of this plot represents the energy difference as the system size approaches infinity. To address potential inaccuracies due to finite bond dimensions, we plot the energy difference versus $\frac{1}{N}$ for several bond dimensions. If the intercept with y-axis converges as the bond dimension increases, we can conclude that the converging value of energy difference reflects the behavior at infinite bond dimension. The results are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

For the spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ system, we calculated the first 4 energy

Figure 4. Energy difference between the third excited state and ground state of a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ system as a function of the inverse of system size $\frac{1}{N}$. We plotted results for three different bond dimensions: 40, 60, and 80. The intercepts with y-axis converges to 0.0054, indicating a vanishing energy difference up to 10^{-1} .

levels. We evaluated the energy difference between the ground state and the third excited state and observed that the difference vanishes at thermodynamic limit. Since the energies of first and second excited state must lie between those of the ground state and third excited state, we conclude that the spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ system is gapless up to the four lowest energy eigenstates. For the spin-1 system, we calculated the first five

Figure 5. Energy difference between the 4th and 3rd excited states for a spin-1 system, plotted versus the inverse system size $\frac{1}{N}$. The results are shown for three different bond dimensions: 40, 60, and 80. The intercept with y-axis converges to 0.3513, indicating a finite energy gap in the thermodynamic limit.

energy levels. The inclusion of the fourth excited state in the calculation for spin-1 is because spin-1 Heisenberg chain as a 4-fold degenerate ground state in the thermodynamic limit, so the lowest pair of energy eigenstates that we can expect to observe a non-vanishing gap is the third and fourth excited states.

We indeed observe such a non-vanishing gap in our calculation, indicating that the spin-1 system is gapped.

In conclusion, by directly calculating the energy levels, we verified that the spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ Heisenberg chain is gapless, while the spin-1 chain is gapped.

B. Entanglement Entropy Scaling

Entanglement entropy is the quantum analogue of the von Neumann entropy, defined as:

$$S = -\sum_i p_i \log p_i,$$

where p_i denotes the probability of configuration i in the system. In the context of quantum mechanics, a configuration is replaced by a quantum state, and the sum over probabilities becomes the trace of the density matrix of the system, $\rho = \sum_i p_i |\psi_i\rangle \langle \psi_i|$, where p_i represents the probability of the quantum state ψ_i . Since we aim to study the entanglement between two subsystems obtained from bipartitioning the MPS, we use the reduced density matrix for subsystem A, ρ_A , instead of the full density matrix of the MPS. The reduced density matrix ρ_A can be obtained from ρ by tracing out the subsystem B. Therefore, the expression for the entanglement entropy is given by [19]:

$$S = -\text{Tr}(\rho_A \log \rho_A), \quad (4)$$

Although generally the choice of subsystem A is flexible, in this study we choose A to be the left half of the system.

The expected scaling behavior of the entanglement entropy with system size differs for integer and half-integer spin chains. For integer spin chains, the entanglement entropy should saturate beyond a certain system size, whereas for half-integer spin chains, the entanglement entropy should continue to grow [21]. For Heisenberg chain in particular, they grows as the log of the system size, satisfying the area law with log correction [22]. To study this scaling behavior, we first calculate the ground state MPS, then evaluate the entanglement entropy for various system sizes. Specifically, we calculated the entanglement entropy scaling behavior for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$, spin-1, and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ systems, where for each system size N , we partitioned the chain and calculated the entanglement entropy between the left and right half (see Fig. 6).

The results indicate that spin- $\frac{1}{2}$, spin- $\frac{3}{2}$, and spin-1 follow the expected scaling relations. As previously discussed, local gapped Hamiltonians obey the area law. According to the Haldane conjecture, integer spin systems are gapped, so spin-1 is expected to satisfy the area law. In one dimension, the "area" is simply a point, meaning that the entanglement entropy should remain constant at large system sizes. The small increase in entanglement entropy observed for spin-1 at small system sizes can be attributed to finite-size effects. In contrast, spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ are gapless and

Figure 6. Entanglement entropy scaling with system size N (log scale) for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$, spin-1, and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ systems. For spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$, we observe a perfectly linear relationship, indicating that the entanglement entropy increases without bound. For spin-1, the entanglement entropy saturates at large system sizes.

do not necessarily obey the area law. The fact that their entanglement entropy increases linearly as $\log_2 N$, indicating that spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ satisfies instead the area law with log correction.

C. Correlation Function Decay

The correlation function can be defined for any pair of local observable operators \mathbf{O}_i and \mathbf{O}_{i+d} as $C_{i,(i+d)} = \langle \psi | \mathbf{O}_i \mathbf{O}_{i+d} | \psi \rangle$. In this study, we specifically calculate the correlation for the z-component of the spin, expressed as [24]:

$$C_{i,(i+d)} = \langle \psi | \mathbf{S}^z_i \mathbf{S}^z_{i+d} | \psi \rangle$$

This expression quantifies the degree of correlation between the z-projection of spins at sites i and $i+d$.

We expect the correlation function of the ground state MPS, $C_{i,(i+d)}$, to decay exponentially in integer spin chains, as these systems exhibit no long-range correlations. In contrast, for half-integer spin chains, $C_{i,(i+d)}$ should decay polynomially as a function of d , due to the presence of long-range correlations. Plotting the correlation function against distance using either a log-log scale or a semi-log scale on the y-axis, we expect half-integer spins to show a linear relationship on the log-log scale, while integer spins should exhibit a linear relationship on the semi-log scale.

To calculate the correlation function, we first set the MPS to a large system size N and calculate its ground state using DMRG. Then, we select a site i sufficiently far from the chain's boundaries to minimize boundary effects. Next, we evaluate its correlation with each site to its right, stopping before reaching a site $i+d$ too close to the other end. In this calculation, we choose $N = 80$, $i = 20$, and $d = 30$

For half-integer spins, the results indicate that spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ aligns with the expected linear relationship. While spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ generally follows a linear trend, its correlation function exhibits periodic oscillations around the fitted line. This oscillatory behavior may arise because the step used to increase the system size is not an integer multiple of the size of unit cell in the spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ system. As the number of sites needed to complete the last unit cell periodically varies with system size, we observe corresponding oscillations in the correlation function (see Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Correlation function between the 20^{th} and $(20 + d)^{\text{th}}$ sites $C_{20,20+d}$ of half-integer spin chains of size 80, as a function of distance d between the two sites. Both spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ follow a linear relation on the log-log scale, indicating that the decay is polynomial.

For integer spins, we observe that the correlation function's dependence on distance decreases linearly on the semi-log scale only after certain data points, indicating that linearity is not strictly obeyed for small system sizes. This behavior is expected because we are primarily concerned with the thermodynamic limit. The reason why spin-2 begins following a linear relationship at larger system sizes compared to spin-1 is that spin-2 has a longer correlation length than spin-1 (see Fig. 8).

Concluding, we observe that the correlation function $C_{20,20+d}$ decays polynomially with d for half-integer spins and decays exponentially with d for integer spins, as expected from gapless and gapped system, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we used the DMRG algorithm to verify the Haldane conjecture, which states that Heisenberg chains with integer spins are gapped, while those with half-integer spins are gapless. We approached this in three ways. First, we explicitly calculated the energy level differences for spin-1 and spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ chains. We found that the energy difference between the 3rd and 4th excited states of the spin-1 chain remains finite in the thermodynamic limit, confirming that it is gapped. We choose the 3rd and 4th excited states because the

Figure 8. Correlation function between the 20^{th} and $(20 + d)^{\text{th}}$ sites $C_{20,20+d}$ of integer spin chains of size 80, as a function of distance d between the two sites. Both spin-1 and spin-2 follow a linear dependence after a certain system size on the semi-log scale, indicating that the decay is exponential at large system sizes.

4 lowest energy levels of spin-1 Heisenberg chain are degenerate. We also observed that spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ chains are gapless up to the 4 lowest energy levels. This is verified by the observed vanishing energy difference between the ground state and 3rd excited state at thermodynamic limit.

Second, we computed the entanglement entropy of the ground state MPS for various system sizes. For spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ chains, the entanglement entropy grows logarithmically with system size. In contrast, for the spin-1 chain, the entanglement entropy saturates at a certain system size. This result is consistent with expectations: half-integer spin chains are gapless and obey the log-corrected area law, whereas integer spin chains are gapped and must therefore satisfy the area law.

Finally, we calculated the correlation function as a function of distance between two sites. For spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{3}{2}$ chains, we observed that the correlation function decays polynomially with distance, indicating the presence of long-range correlations, which is expected from a gapless system. Conversely, the correlation function for spin-1 and spin-2 chains decays exponentially, suggesting the absence of long-range correlations, which is indicative of gapped systems.

In this study, we focused on lower spin systems due to limited computational resources. Future research could test the Haldane conjecture for higher spin systems. Additionally, we used a limited bond dimension when optimizing the MPS using DMRG, which may cause the entanglement entropy to deviate from expected behavior at large system sizes. Future studies could use larger bond dimensions to investigate whether this improves the agreement with theoretical expectations.

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Appendix A: Decomposition of Quantum State into MPS

The Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) states that any $n \times m$ matrix M can be decomposed into the product of an $n \times d$ unitary matrix U , an $r \times r$ diagonal matrix S , and an $r \times m$ unitary matrix V^\dagger [23].

$$M = USV^\dagger \quad (\text{A1})$$

Or, in terms of matrix elements:

$$M_{a,b} = \sum_{r=1}^d U_{a,r} S_{r,r} V_{r,b}^\dagger \quad (\text{A2})$$

where each element $S_{r,r}$ is called a singular value

For a general quantum state characterized by n indices $|\psi\rangle = \sum_{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n} c_{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n} |\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n\rangle$, we treat the coefficient $c_{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n}$ as a rank- n tensor, which encapsulates all the information about the quantum state. We can then decompose this tensor into smaller, interconnected tensors using SVD by sequentially separating each index. For instance, to separate the index σ_1 , we group all other indices together, so that $c_{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n}$ becomes $c_{\sigma_1, (\sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n)}$, which is a matrix on which we can perform SVD:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{\sigma_1, (\sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n)} &= \sum_{a_1=1}^{r_1} A_{a_1}^{\sigma_1} \left(S_{a_1, a_1} V_{a_1, (\sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n)}^\dagger \right) \\ &= \sum_{a_1=1}^{r_1} A_{a_1}^{\sigma_1} M_{(a_1, \sigma_2), (\sigma_3, \dots, \sigma_n)} \\ &= \sum_{a_1=1}^{r_1} \sum_{a_2=1}^{r_2} A_{a_1}^{\sigma_1} A_{a_1, a_2}^{\sigma_2} \left(S_{a_2, a_2} V_{a_2, (\sigma_3, \dots, \sigma_n)}^\dagger \right) \\ &= \sum_{a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}} A_{a_1}^{\sigma_1} A_{a_1, a_2}^{\sigma_2} \dots A_{a_{n-2}, a_{n-1}}^{\sigma_{n-1}} A_{a_{n-1}}^{\sigma_n} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

After separating σ_1 , the resulting diagonal tensor S is combined with the tensor on the right to form a new tensor M , and then SVD is performed again on index σ_2 . By following this process iteratively, all indices can be separated and the coefficient tensor will be decomposed into a product of smaller tensors, resulting in an MPS [9]. The σ_i indices exist in the original quantum state and are therefore called physical indices, while the a_i indices are generated during the decomposition process and are called bond indices. These bond indices carry information about the entanglement structure in the system [25].

Appendix B: Write Hamiltonian as an MPO

A general Hamiltonian, written in the same basis used to express the quantum state in the previous section, $|\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n\rangle$, is given by

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{\vec{\sigma}, \vec{\sigma}'} c_{\vec{\sigma}, \vec{\sigma}'} |\vec{\sigma}\rangle \langle \vec{\sigma}'| \quad (\text{B1})$$

Figure 9. Tensor network representation of decomposing a general quantum state into an MPS. SVD is performed sequentially on each σ_i index. The A tensors correspond to the left unitary matrices obtained from the SVD, the S matrices represent the diagonal matrices, and the V^\dagger matrices are the right unitary matrices. After multiplying S and V^\dagger into M , we do the next SVD on the new M

By grouping each σ_i, σ'_i pair together, we reduce the problem to a form similar to the quantum state decomposition case. However, it is important to note that in order to express the Hamiltonian in the $|\vec{\sigma}\rangle \langle \vec{\sigma}'|$ basis, we need to separate the pairs again, resulting in an additional physical index on each site. This aligns with the requirement that the Hamiltonian acting on a quantum state produces a new quantum state. Such a representation of an operator is referred to as an MPO.

$$\mathbf{H} = \sum_{\vec{\sigma}, \vec{\sigma}'} \sum_{a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}} W_{a_1}^{\sigma_1, \sigma'_1} W_{a_1, a_2}^{\sigma_2, \sigma'_2} \dots W_{a_{n-1}}^{\sigma_n, \sigma'_n} \quad (\text{B2})$$

Instead of performing the decomposition directly, a more convenient method for constructing the MPO for a Hamiltonian with local interactions is by analyzing how to build each interaction term. Let's consider the Heisenberg Hamiltonian, which will be used later in this study, as an example:

$$\mathbf{H} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{J}{2} (S_i^+ S_{i+1}^- + S_i^- S_{i+1}^+) + J_z S_i^z S_{i+1}^z \quad (\text{B3})$$

We construct these interaction terms from right to left. Suppose we have already placed some tensors on the right; we now examine the status of building each interaction term. There are five possible states:

1. Only identity operators on the right.
2. One S^+ operator to the right.
3. One S^- operator to the right.
4. One S^z operator to the right.
5. The interaction term is completed.

Next, we determine how to transition to state 5 from each of these possibilities:

- 1 \rightarrow 5: No transition possible.
- 2 \rightarrow 5: Multiply by $\frac{J}{2} S^-$.
- 3 \rightarrow 5: Multiply by $\frac{J}{2} S^+$.

- 4 \rightarrow 5: Multiply by $J_z S^z$.
- 5 \rightarrow 5: Already in state 5, multiply by the identity operator.

Now, starting from state 1, the transitions to other states are as follows:

- 1 \rightarrow 1: Already in state 1, multiply by the identity operator.
- 1 \rightarrow 2: Multiply by S^+ .
- 1 \rightarrow 3: Multiply by S^- .
- 1 \rightarrow 4: Multiply by S^z .
- 1 \rightarrow 5: No transition possible.

The rightmost tensor can be in one of four states, which we encode in a column vector (state 5 has a zero probability):

$$W^{\sigma_n, \sigma'_n} = \begin{pmatrix} I \\ S_n^+ \\ S_n^- \\ S_n^z \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B4})$$

When constructing the tensor to the left, the first column should transform state 1 to each of the other states, and the last row should complete each state to state 5. Thus, a general bulk MPO tensor is:

$$W^{\sigma_i, \sigma'_i} = \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ S_i^+ & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ S_i^- & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ S_i^z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{J}{2} S_i^- & \frac{J}{2} S_i^+ & J_z S_i^z & I \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B5})$$

In the leftmost tensor, we should complete every path without starting a new one from state 1. Therefore, it should be a row vector identical to the last row of the bulk tensor:

$$W^{\sigma_1, \sigma'_1} = (0 \quad \frac{J}{2} S_1^- \quad \frac{J}{2} S_1^+ \quad J_z S_1^z \quad I) \quad (\text{B6})$$

Appendix C: DMRG Ground State Search Details

1. Gauge Invariance and Canonical Form

Before delving into the details of DMRG, it is essential to introduce two important concepts: gauge invariance and canonical forms. All tensor networks possess the property of gauge invariance, which means that inserting a pair of inverse matrices into any bond of the network leaves the tensor network state unchanged. This property allows the same tensor network state to be expressed in different forms, the most common of which are the canonical forms.

The **left canonical form** is obtained by performing Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) from left to right. After decomposing $M^{\sigma_i} = A^{\sigma_i} S V^\dagger$, we keep only the A matrices on the left. Since all the A matrices are isometry, the left canonical form satisfies the condition

$$\sum_{\sigma_i} A^{\sigma_i \dagger} A^{\sigma_i} = I.$$

Similarly, the **right canonical form** is derived by performing SVD from right to left, $M^{\sigma_i} = USB^{\sigma_i \dagger}$, where we retain only the B^\dagger matrices. The right canonical form satisfies the property $\sum_{\sigma_i} B^{\sigma_i} B^{\sigma_i \dagger} = I$

A particularly important form for DMRG is the **mixed canonical form**, in which tensors to the left of a specific site are in the left canonical form, while tensors to the right of that site are in the right canonical form. The key advantage of this mixed form is that it simplifies the calculation of the expectation value of the state, reducing it to the overlap at the specific splitting site.

Figure 10. Calculation of the expectation value of a quantum state $\langle \psi | \psi \rangle$ in mixed canonical form, represented in tensor network graph notation. The parts circled in orange are all equal to the identity.

2. DMRG Sweeping Procedure

The detailed sweeping procedure for using DMRG to find the ground state of an MPS is as follows:

1. Write the entire state in the right canonical form.
2. **Right sweep:** Optimize from site 1 to N . For each site, after obtaining the locally optimized tensor M^{σ_i} , update the local tensor. Perform SVD on $M^{\sigma_i} = A^{\sigma_i} S V^\dagger$, where the diagonal matrix S contains the entanglement information between the left and right parts of the MPS chain. The number of non-zero diagonal entries in S is called the bond dimension. Finally, combine the resulting matrices to update the tensor on the next site: $\tilde{M}^{\sigma_{i+1}} = S V^\dagger M^{\sigma_{i+1}}$, and proceed to optimize the new tensor.
3. **Left sweep:** Optimize from site N back to site 1. Similarly, after obtaining the locally optimized tensor M^{σ_i} , perform SVD on $M^{\sigma_i} = U S B^{\sigma_i \dagger}$, and update the tensor on the previous site by combining matrices: $\tilde{M}^{\sigma_{i-1}} = M^{\sigma_{i-1}} U S$.
4. Repeat the sweeping process (right and left sweeps) until the energy converges.

During the SVD step, the singular values are typically reordered in decreasing order. The smallest singular values that introduce errors within the desired tolerance can be discarded. Since these singular values encode the entanglement between the two partitions of the system at the optimization site, removing small singular values effectively eliminates weak entanglements. This is the core principle of DMRG.

Figure 11. Illustration of the right sweep process in a 4-site chain. M^{σ_2} is the optimized tensor at site 2. After performing SVD, the resulting S and V^\dagger are combined with the tensor at site 3 to form a new tensor, which will then be optimized. Smaller singular values in S may be discarded as needed.

3. Single Site Optimization

We have outlined the general process of DMRG, but we have not yet explained the local optimization step. Here, we focus on single-site optimization, which aims to adjust the tensor at a specific site to minimize the energy. By taking the derivative of the energy with respect to the local tensor $M_{a_{i-1}, a_i}^{\sigma_i}$, we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \langle \psi | \mathbf{H} | \psi \rangle}{\partial M_{a_{i-1}, a_i}^{\sigma_i}} - \langle \psi | \mathbf{H} | \psi \rangle \frac{\partial \langle \psi | \psi \rangle}{\partial M_{a_{i-1}, a_i}^{\sigma_i}} = 0 \quad (\text{C1})$$

where $\lambda = \langle \psi | \mathbf{H} | \psi \rangle$ can be computed directly. To evaluate $\frac{\partial \langle \psi | \mathbf{H} | \psi \rangle}{\partial M_{a_{i-1}, a_i}^{\sigma_i}}$, we contract everything to the left

of site i into a large tensor $L_{b_{i-1}}^{a_{i-1}, a'_{i-1}}$, and everything to the right of site i into a large tensor $R_{b_i}^{a_i, a'_i}$. These two tensors, when contracted with the Hamiltonian tensor at site i , form an effective Hamiltonian:

$$\mathbf{H}_{(\sigma_i a_{i-1}, a_i), (\sigma'_i a'_{i-1}, a'_i)}^{eff} = \sum_{b_{i-1}, b_i} L_{b_{i-1}}^{a_{i-1}, a'_{i-1}} W_{b_{i-1}, b_i}^{\sigma_i, \sigma'_i} R_{b_i}^{a_i, a'_i} \quad (\text{C2})$$

This effective Hamiltonian acts on the MPS tensor at site i . We reshape the effective Hamiltonian into a matrix (as shown in C2), and also reshape the local MPS tensor at site i as $M_{a'_{i-1}, a'_i}^{\sigma_i} = v(\sigma'_i a'_{i-1} a'_i)$. The action of the effective Hamiltonian on this local tensor can then be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial \langle \psi | \mathbf{H} | \psi \rangle}{\partial M_{a_{i-1}, a_i}^{\sigma_i}} \\ &= \sum_{\sigma'_i, a'_{i-1}, a'_i, b_{i-1}, b_i} L_{b_{i-1}}^{a_{i-1}, a'_{i-1}} W_{b_{i-1}, b_i}^{\sigma_i, \sigma'_i} R_{b_i}^{a_i, a'_i} M_{a'_{i-1}, a'_i}^{\sigma'_i} \\ &= \mathbf{H}^{eff} \vec{v} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C3})$$

The other term in the optimization equation, $\frac{\partial \langle \psi | \psi \rangle}{\partial M_{a_{i-1}, a_i}^{\sigma_i}}$, simplifies to just the local tensor $M_{a'_{i-1}, a'_i}^{\sigma'_i} = v(\sigma'_i a'_{i-1} a'_i)$ if we assume that the MPS is in a mixed canonical form centered at this site. This assumption reduces the optimization problem to solving the eigenvalue equation:

$$\mathbf{H}^{eff} \vec{v} = \lambda \vec{v} \quad (\text{C4})$$

This assumption is valid because the SVD step in the sweeping process ensures that the MPS is always in a mixed canonical form centered at the site we intend to optimize.

Figure 12. Two terms in the optimization equation are illustrated (the empty site indicates where the derivative is taken). The upper diagram represents $\frac{\partial \langle \psi | \hat{H} | \psi \rangle}{\partial M_{\sigma_i, \sigma'_i}}$, while the lower diagram corresponds to $\frac{\partial \langle \psi | \psi \rangle}{\partial M_{\sigma_{i-1}, \sigma'_{i-1}}}$. We assume that the MPS is in mixed canonical form, such that $\Psi_{\sigma_{i-1}, \sigma'_{i-1}}^A = \Psi_{\sigma_i, \sigma'_i}^B = I$. The tensor highlighted in orange is the one we want to optimize.

4. Two Sites Optimization

Two-site optimization offers significant advantages over single-site optimization, particularly when it comes to preserving and exploring symmetries in a system.

Single-site optimization is often heavily constrained by symmetry considerations. For instance, if the total spin is conserved, there is typically only one choice for the physical index that satisfies this symmetry. This rigid constraint limits the flexibility of the optimization process, making it more prone to getting stuck in local minima because only one tensor can be adjusted at a time, leading to a narrow path through the energy landscape.

In contrast, two-site optimization allows for the simultaneous adjustment of two neighboring tensors, providing more degrees of freedom. For example, in a system where the total spin is conserved, optimizing two sites together offers more options because the combined physical indices of the two sites can give rise to the same total spin in different ways (e.g., a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ can combine to form either a spin-1 or spin-0 state). This additional flexibility makes it easier for the optimization algorithm to navigate the energy landscape and avoid local minima.

To implement two-site optimization, we simply combine the two tensors into one and apply the same process used in single-site optimization.

Figure 13. Illustration of a two-site optimization process. The two sites highlighted in orange are currently being optimized. We combine them into a single site and solve the single-site optimization equation.

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